

RESEARCH

Enhancing high-tunnel tomato productivity through nitrogen and phosphorus optimization in western Amhara, Ethiopia

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Abstract

Background: High-tunnel tomato production technology has emerged as a vital technology in western Amhara, Ethiopia, to address the production challenges during the rainy season. However, its productivity is low, mainly because of the absence of recommended rates of N and P nutrients. Therefore, two-year experiments were conducted in the 2023 and 2024 main seasons to optimize N and P nutrients. **Methods:** The experiment involved four levels of nitrogen (0, 160, 320, and 480 kg N ha⁻¹) and four levels of phosphorus (0, 40, 80, and 120 kg P₂O₅ ha⁻¹), arranged in a factorial RCBD with three replications. Phenology, growth, yield, and quality data were collected and analyzed using R software V.4.0. **Results:** The results revealed that the combined application of N and P fertilizers significantly ($P < 0.01$) affected the productivity of tomato. The combined application of 320/120 kg ha⁻¹ N/P₂O₅ was the optimal combination for flower number cluster⁻¹ (7.71), fruit number cluster⁻¹ (6.27), fruit set percentage (81.15%), marketable yield (88.21 tons ha⁻¹), total yield (90.71 tons ha⁻¹), fruit firmness (13.01 N), and total soluble solids (4.37 °Brix). Conversely, the lowest performance was observed in the untreated plots and plots treated with either of the two nutrients. The regression analysis found that the combination rate can be extended up to 358/128 kg ha⁻¹ N/P₂O₅ for maximum yield. **Conclusion:** This combination greatly enhanced tomato productivity and provided the highest net benefit of 3,506,745.00 ETB ha⁻¹ with a marginal rate of return of 2370.5%, which is recommended for high-tunnel tomato production in the study area.

Keywords: high-tunnel tomato production, marketable yield, net benefit, nutrient optimization, optimum interaction, total soluble solids

Introduction

Tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum* L.) is the most widely consumed vegetable crop worldwide because it is a rich source of carbohydrates, proteins, vitamins, minerals, and antioxidants (Bauchet and Causse, 2012; Bihon *et al.*, 2022). According to FAOSTAT (2023), more than 190 million tons of tomato fruits are produced over 5.4 million hectares of land worldwide. Asia accounts for 63% of global tomato production, followed by the Americas (13.9%), Africa (12%), and Europe (11.1%) (Aksoy and Kaymak, 2024). Egypt, Nigeria, and Algeria are the top three tomato producers in Africa (FAOSTAT, 2023). Ethiopia is also a major tomato producer in eastern Africa, with an annual production of 41,948 tons (FAOSTAT, 2023), where the Amhara region contributes approximately 10% of national tomato production (CSA, 2022).

In Ethiopia, tomatoes are cultivated mainly during the dry season in open fields under irrigation conditions. Production is not common during the rainy season because of the incidence of primarily fungal and bacterial wilt diseases, such as *Fusarium* wilt, *Verticillium* wilt, and Bacterial wilt (Alemayehu and Alemayehu, 2017; Sindhu and Ranjit, 2020; CSA, 2022). Moreover, the productivity of open field tomatoes in Ethiopia is low, with an average of 6 tons ha⁻¹, which is far below the world average (>101 tons ha⁻¹) (FAOSTAT, 2023; Aksoy and Kaymak, 2024). These conditions create a shortage of tomato market supplies and price escalation during the rainy season (Bachewe and Minten, 2021). To address these challenges, alternative technologies for the production of tomatoes during the rainy season, including high-tunnel tomato production, have been suggested and practiced (Alemayehu and Alemayehu, 2017).

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In recent years, high-tunnel tomato cultivation technology has been adopted in western Amhara, Ethiopia, which enables the production of tomatoes during the rainy season (Anteneh *et al.*, 2021). High-tunnel cultivation involves the cultivation of crops in a partially controlled environment (Singh *et al.*, 2018; Sahu *et al.*, 2020). It offers distinct advantages, such as year-round availability, efficient resource utilization, better quality, and higher productivity (Sindhu and Ranjit, 2020; Kumar *et al.*, 2021). High-tunnel tomato technology helps farmers increase the volume of tomato fruits produced and marketed.

However, the average productivity of high-tunnel tomato cultivation in western Amhara, Ethiopia, is still low because of both biotic and abiotic factors. These include poor nutrient management, diseases, insect pests, and a lack of improved and adapted varieties (Golla, 2020; Dabesa and Regasa, 2021), where poor nutrient management practices are the determining factor.

Plant nutrition is one of the key factors influencing the growth, yield, and quality of crop plants (Shankara *et al.*, 2019; Kaur and Kaur, 2021). Tomatoes are heavy feeders of mainly macronutrients and some micronutrients (Islam *et al.*, 2017; Acedo and Benitez, 2021). Nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P) are two essential plant nutrient elements that play significant roles in determining crop yield (Panta and Parajulee, 2021; Abebe *et al.*, 2022). On the other hand, too little or too much nutrient application negatively impacts the yield and quality of tomato fruits. The effects of these nutrients on the growth, yield, and quality of tomatoes have been demonstrated and confirmed by different authors, although their rate of recommendation varies (Dhiman *et al.*, 2018; Sigaye *et al.*, 2022; Yue *et al.*, 2022).

In this context, Sigaye *et al.* (2022) reported that a significantly greater yield (59.7 t ha⁻¹) was obtained from the combined application of 138/40 kg ha⁻¹ N/P₂O₅ under the open field conditions. Gebremedhin *et al.* (2020) reported that the combined application of N and P, with 138/69 kg ha⁻¹ N/P₂O₅, resulted in a yield advantage of 68.4% over the control. An investigation conducted under polyhouse conditions demonstrated a greater fruit yield (93.8 t ha⁻¹) from the combined application of 125/47 kg ha⁻¹ N/P₂O₅ (Dhiman *et al.*, 2018). Nishat *et al.* (2021) reported that the application of 300/125 kg ha⁻¹ N/P₂O₅ resulted in the highest fruit yield of tomatoes in Bangladesh.

In western Amhara, Ethiopia, where farmers practice high-tunnel production, there is limited information on the optimum rates of N and P₂O₅ for the production of tomatoes using this technology. Farmers are using fertilizer recommendations for the production of open-pollinated tomato varieties in open field production systems due to the absence of a recommended rate for high-tunnel technology. Therefore, this study was conducted with the aim of identifying the optimum rates of N and P fertilizers for the economical production of hybrid tomato varieties in high-tunnel production systems in western Amhara, Ethiopia.

Methods

DESCRIPTION OF THE STUDY AREA

The experiments were conducted during the 2023 and 2024 main cropping seasons. The experiments were conducted during the 2023 and 2024 main cropping seasons under a high-tunnel environment in the Koga Irrigation Scheme of the North Mecha district of western Amhara, Ethiopia. Geographically, the Koga Irrigation Scheme is located between 11° 18' 0" and 11° 36' 0" North latitude and 37° 5' 0" and 37° 15' 0" East longitude in the Blue Nile basin (Fig. 1). The elevation of the experimental site is 1900 masl. According to the National Meteorological Agency, Western Amhara Branch, the amount of rainfall and average monthly temperature of the study area during the experiment (*i.e.*, June–September) were 1416.1 mm and 18.9°C, respectively. Moreover, the mean monthly temperature and relative humidity of

the environment inside the high-tunnel ranged from 17.9–35.8°C to 24.1–50%, respectively (Fig. 2).

The experiments were conducted in the natural ground soil, and to evaluate the physicochemical properties, representative soil samples were collected from the top 20 cm depth in a diagonal pattern from ten spots across the experimental field using an auger before plowing and transplanting. The collected soil samples were composited and analyzed for selected parameters at Bahir Dar University College of Agriculture and Environmental Science Soil and Plant Analysis Laboratory.

The texture was determined by the Boycouos hydrometer method (Day, 1965), and the pH was determined from a suspension with a 1:2.5 soil:water ratio using a pH meter (Rhoades, 1982). Organic carbon was determined by the dichromate oxidation method and subsequent titration with ferrous ammonium sulfate (Walkley and Black, 1934), and organic matter was obtained by multiplying the percentage of OC by 1.724, assuming that the C concentration of OM was 58%. The total N content was estimated by the Kjeldahl method (Black, 1965), the available P content was estimated using the Olsen extraction method (Olsen and Sommers, 1982), and the cation exchange capacity was estimated by the leaching method (Van Reeuwijk, 2002). The results of the soil analysis are presented in Table 1.

EXPERIMENTAL MATERIALS, TREATMENTS, AND DESIGN

A hybrid tomato variety, Galilia, was used for this study, which is mostly used by farmers in the study area because of its high yield capacity and longer shelf life. Under open field conditions, the variety has yield potentials of 69.5 and 65.9 t ha⁻¹ in on-station and on-farm trials, respectively (SHEP PLUS, 2019). Moreover, urea (46%) and Triple Super Phosphate (TSP) (46% P₂O₅) fertilizers were used as sources of nitrogen and phosphorus. Wood and elephant suti were used as the staking materials for plant support.

The experiment consisted of four levels of N (0, 160, 320, and 480 kg ha⁻¹) and four levels of P₂O₅ (0, 40, 80, and 120 kg ha⁻¹), which were arranged in 4 × 4 factorial combinations using a randomized complete block design (RCBD) with three replications. The plot size was 2.5 × 4 m (10 m²), with a net plot size of 6 m² (2 × 3 m). Each plot contained four rows and five plants per row, with a total of 20 plants per plot. The intrarow and interrow spacings were 0.5 and 1 m, respectively. The spacing was maintained at 1 m between plots and 1.5 m between blocks.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

An appropriate site for high-tunnel construction was selected considering soil type, slope, solar radiation access, windbreaks, and water availability. After land clearing, a high tunnel covering an area 15 m in width and 56 m in length was constructed during the 2023 and 2024 cropping seasons using locally available materials and covered with a standard greenhouse plastic sheet with a thickness of 2 mm (Manufactured by Amhara Pipe Factory, Amhara Ethiopia). The height of the high tunnel was 8 m at the center.

The experimental plot was prepared through two rounds of plowing at depths ranging from 15 to 30 cm, followed by harrowing to produce a fine seedbed. After the layout was designed, the raised seedbeds at a height of 40 cm were prepared and hand irrigated at field capacity to make them ready for seedling transplantation. Healthy, acclimatized, and 25-day-old seedlings were sourced from Roshanara Rose PLC, a commercial farm, and transplanted at the beginning of June.

The treatments were applied randomly to the experimental unit. Fertilizer was applied using the banding method for both nitrogen and phosphorus. The total quantity of phosphorus calculated on the basis of the experimental treatment was applied during the time of transplanting. Nitrogen in the form of urea was applied in three splits, where the first half of the quantity was applied at the time of

Fig. 1. Map of the study area.

Fig. 2. Minimum and maximum temperatures and relative humidity of the environment inside the high tunnel during the experiment.

Table 1. Selected soil physicochemical properties of the study site before planting.

Silt (%)	Clay (%)	Sand (%)	Textural class	pH-H ₂ O	EC (μS/cm)	OC (%)	OM (%)	TN (%)	AP (ppm)	CEC (Cmol (+) kg ⁻¹)
41	50	9	Silt clay	5.82	42.2	0.74	1.28	0.19	5.5	20.8

EC: electrical conductivity, OC: organic carbon, OM: organic matter, TN: total nitrogen, and AP: available phosphorus.

transplanting, while one-fourth (¼) of the quantity was applied at the midgrowth stage (30 days after transplanting) of the plants. The remaining one-fourth (¼) of nitrogen was applied at the flowering stage (Hasnain *et al.*, 2020). All other agronomic practices were applied on the basis of the recommendations and uniformly for each experimental unit (Shankara *et al.*, 2019). Irrigation was applied daily for the first 2 weeks and then extended to 1-day intervals until harvest. Water was applied into a 10-cm-deep hole prepared between plants using a hand irrigation system with a cane, to minimize contact between water and the tomato plants, as practiced locally. Intercultivation practices were performed concurrently with fertilizer application.

Insect pest and disease management were done through pesticide applications. Apollo 50 SC (Manufactured by Indofil Industries Ltd., Maharashtra, India) was applied prior to seedling transplanting to control seedling cutters. Two applications of Shadow 75 WP (Manufactured by Indofil Industries Ltd., Maharashtra, India) were made at 2-week intervals, starting 1 month after transplanting, to manage powdery mildew. Harvesting was conducted at the turning stage, with the crop cycle comprising nine harvest rounds.

DATA COLLECTION

Phenological parameters

The number of days to 50% flowering was recorded by counting the number of days that elapsed from the date of transplanting to the date when 50% of the plants in the plot set flowers. Days to 50% fruiting were collected by counting the number of days elapsed from the date of transplanting to the date at which 50% of the plants in the plot had at least one fruit. The number of days to first harvest was recorded by counting the number of days elapsed from transplanting to the date of the turning stage.

Growth parameters

The number of primary branches was recorded from the day to the first harvest by counting the number of branches extending from the main stem of the tomato plants. The height (m) of six plants in the net plot area was measured from the ground level (root collar) to the tip of the plant using a measuring tape (Model DS-1008-099) (Manufactured by Shenzhen Deli Measuring Tools Co., Ltd., Guangdong, China) from the first harvest. The number of clusters from six plants in the net plot area was also counted during the first harvest.

Fruit yield and yield-related parameters

The number of flowers per cluster at full bloom was counted from 15 randomly selected clusters per plant. The number of fruits per cluster was also recorded by counting the number of fruits from 15 randomly selected and tagged clusters during harvesting. The fruit set percentage was calculated as described previously (Sato *et al.*, 2002).

$$\text{FSP}(\%) = \frac{\text{NFrC}}{\text{NFIC}} * 100 \quad (1)$$

where FSP = fruit set percentage, NFrC = number of fruits per cluster, and NFIC = number of flowers per cluster.

The marketable fruit yield (tons ha⁻¹) was determined by sorting and weighing fruits that were free from damage caused by

diseases, insects, cracking, and blossoming end rot, whereas the damaged and small fruits were considered unmarketable fruit yield (tons ha⁻¹). The total fruit yield (tons ha⁻¹) was calculated by summing the marketable and unmarketable yields.

Fruit physicochemical quality traits

The average fruit weight (g) and fruit diameter (mm) were recorded by weighing and measuring the cross sections of 15 fruits per plant at each harvest in the net plot area. Fruit firmness (Newton) was obtained by calculating the force required to penetrate the fruits selected randomly at each harvest using a fruit penetrometer (Model GY-4S/NG2001707622) (Manufactured by Gotech International Corporation, Taiwan) with an 8-mm stainless steel punch. The fruits were penetrated on the equatorial region, and the average value was taken. The mean pericarp thickness (mm) was recorded by cutting cross sections of 15 randomly selected fruits and measuring their thicknesses using a caliper (Model Mitutoyo 500-197-30) (Manufactured by Mitutoyo Corporation, Kanagawa Prefecture, Japan).

The juice pH was recorded by extracting clear juice from fifteen randomly selected fruits and measuring it with a pH meter. Titratable acidity (TA) (%): Tomato juice was extracted from 15 randomly selected fruit samples by a commercial blender (Model GSB-1513) (Manufactured by Guangdong Galanz Enterprises Group Co., Ltd., Shenzhen, China) and filtered through a sieve. Ten milliliters of a clear juice sample was titrated gradually with 0.1 N NaOH using a burette for 15 s, and the titratable acidity was expressed as a percentage of the citric acid content using the following formula (Tyl and Sadler, 2017; Abd-Elsalam *et al.*, 2021):

$$\text{TA}(\%) = \frac{\text{Titre} * 0.1\text{N NaOH}}{1000} * 100 \quad (2)$$

where TA is the titratable acidity, titer is the volume of tomato juice, 0.1 N is the amount of NaOH used to neutralize 0.64 g of citric acid, and 0.64 is the conversion factor.

The total soluble solids (TSS) (°Brix) were measured by extracting juice from sample fruits as indicated by Khan *et al.* (2021) and Nishat *et al.* (2021). The fruit juice was extracted by a high-performance commercial blender and filtered using a sieve. The TSS was then determined by placing two drops of clear juice on the prism of a hand refractometer (Model ATAGO PR-32 α) (Manufactured by ATAGO Co., Ltd., Kyoto, Japan) with a scale of 0 to 32 °Brix. The sugar-to-acid ratio (SAR) was determined using the following formula (Tyl and Sadler, 2017; Abu-Alrub *et al.*, 2019).

$$\text{SAR} = \frac{\text{Total soluble solid}}{\text{Titratable acidity}} \quad (3)$$

DATA ANALYSIS

All the data collected from each year were first checked for normality and homogeneity before analysis using Leven and Bartlett's homogeneity error variance tests. The data were subjected to two-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) using the PROC GLM procedure in R Software version 4.0. Combined analysis of variance over the years was performed following the results of the homogeneity test. The rates of N and P₂O₅ fertilizers were considered fixed effects, and the year was considered a random effect. Mean separation

was carried out using the least significant difference (LSD) test at the 0.05% level of significance.

Linear regression was performed to determine which model fit the data well. Then, quadratic regression was used on the fitted line with a higher coefficient of determination (R^2) value than the linear model to explain the relationship between N and P fertilizer levels and marketable yield using the PROC REG procedure. The N P_2O_5 -response curve (N P_2O_5 levels vs. marketable yield) was used to identify the right rate to produce the highest yield. Moreover, the quadratic fit model was used to estimate the optimum values of the N P_2O_5 interaction above which no additional net return was predicted.

PARTIAL BUDGET ANALYSIS

A partial budget analysis was performed to determine the economics of using N and P fertilizers, where the mean marketable fruit yield of tomato was downscaled by 10% to make it comparable with the yield of farmers, as described by CIMMYT (1988). The costs of fertilizers and labor for the application of fertilizers were considered variable costs to calculate the net benefits of each treatment combination (CIMMYT, 1988).

The prices of urea and TSP were 45 ETB¹ kg⁻¹, whereas the wage rate was 375 ETB per man-day during the experimental period (2023–2024). It was assumed that 1.5 man-day is required to apply 100 kg of urea and TSP. Moreover, the farm gate price of tomato fruit during harvesting was 45 ETB kg⁻¹ on average.

The gross benefit was calculated by multiplying the marketable yield by the farm gate price, whereas the net benefit was calculated by deducting the total variable costs from the gross benefit (Table 2). All costs and benefits were calculated on a hectare basis. Dominance analysis was carried out by listing the treatment combinations in

ascending order of the variable costs. The treatment combination with the lowest net benefit compared with the previous treatment dominated and was excluded from the marginal rate of analysis. The marginal rate of return was then calculated by dividing the change in net benefit by the change in variable cost and multiplying by 100. The marginal rate of returns of each treatment combination was compared with the minimum acceptable value, which is 100% for the developing countries such as Ethiopia (CIMMYT, 1988; Farquharson, 2006; Shah *et al.*, 2009).

Results

INFLUENCES OF N AND P FERTILIZERS ON THE PHENOLOGY AND GROWTH OF TOMATO

The main and interaction effects of the N and P fertilizers did not influence the phenological parameters of tomato ($P > 0.05$) (Table 3). However, the combined analysis of variance (ANOVA) revealed that plant height, branch number, and cluster number were highly significantly ($P < 0.01$) influenced by the main and interaction effects of N and P fertilizer application (Table 3).

The tallest plant height (2.12 m) was recorded from the combined application of 480/80 kg ha⁻¹ N/ P_2O_5 , whereas the shortest plant height (1.76 m) was recorded from the plots supplied with 0/0 kg ha⁻¹ N/ P_2O_5 . The application of optimum N and P promotes vegetative vigor, which can underpin the improved reproductive performance and yield potential.

The pooled data also revealed that the application of 480/80 kg ha⁻¹ N/ P_2O_5 resulted in the highest number of main branches of tomato plants (10.33), which was in statistical parity with plants grown on plots supplied with 320/120 and 320/80 kg ha⁻¹ N/ P_2O_5 . On the other hand, the smallest main branch numbers were recorded from tomato plants supplied with 0/0 and 0/40 kg ha⁻¹

Table 2. Partial budget analysis of high-tunnel tomato varieties influenced by NP fertilizers.

N/P	MY (t ha ⁻¹)	AMY (t ha ⁻¹)	GB (ETB ha ⁻¹)	TVC (ETB ha ⁻¹)	NB (ETB ha ⁻¹)	Dominance analysis	MRR (%)
0/0	38.73	34.857	1,568,565.00	0.00	1,568,565.00		–
0/40	47.25	42.525	1,913,625.00	10,125.00	1,903,500.00		3,308.00
160/0	56.75	51.075	2,298,375.00	17,490.00	2,280,885.00		5,124.03
0/80	54.32	48.888	2,199,960.00	20,250.00	2,179,710.00	D	–
160/40	63.24	56.916	2,561,220.00	29,490.00	2,531,730.00		2,090.38
0/120	54.96	49.464	2,225,880.00	30,375.00	2,195,505.00	D	–
320/0	66.78	60.102	2,704,590.00	34,980.00	2,669,610.00		2,511.48
160/80	68.49	61.641	2,773,845.00	41,490.00	2,732,355.00		963.82
320/40	75.76	68.184	3,068,280.00	46,980.00	3,021,300.00		5,263.11
160/120	73.93	66.537	2,994,165.00	47,865.00	2,946,300.00	D	–
480/0	60.58	54.522	2,453,490.00	52,470.00	2,401,020.00	D	–
320/80	80.88	72.792	3,275,640.00	53,355.00	3,222,285.00		3,152.71
480/40	76.88	69.192	3,113,640.00	58,845.00	3,054,795.00	D	–
320/120	88.2	79.38	3,572,100.00	65,355.00	3,506,745.00		2,370.50
480/80	84.4	75.96	3,418,200.00	70,845.00	3,347,355.00	D	–
480/120	79.67	71.703	3,226,635.00	82,845.00	3,143,790.00	D	–

MY: marketable yield, AMY: adjusted marketable yield, GB: gross benefit, TVC: total varying cost, NB: net benefit, MRR: marginal rate of return, D: dominated.

¹ ETB refers Ethiopian Birr-the unit of currency in Ethiopia; 1USD = 153.5 ETB in October 2025.

Table 3. Effects of NP fertilizers on the phenology and growth of tomato plants.

N/P ₂ O ₅ (kg ha ⁻¹)	Days to 50% flowering	Days to 50% fruiting	Days to first harvest	Plant height (m)	Branch number	Cluster number
0/0	35.17	42.67	60.33	1.76 ^h	3.85 ⁱ	12.92 ^j
0/40	34.33	41.83	59.33	1.80 ^{gh}	5.01 ^h	14.49 ^h
0/80	34.33	41.83	60.5	1.83 ^{fgh}	6.01 ^g	15.24 ^{gh}
0/120	34.33	41.83	60.67	1.84 ^{efg}	6.08 ^{fg}	15.89 ^{fg}
160/0	35.33	43.33	62.33	1.84 ^{efg}	6.23 ^{efg}	16.22 ^{efg}
160/40	34.67	42.83	60.33	1.87 ^{def}	6.96 ^{ef}	17.05 ^{def}
160/80	34.67	42.17	60.67	1.89 ^{def}	7.01 ^{ef}	17.15 ^{def}
160/120	34.67	42.17	60.17	1.91 ^{cde}	7.14 ^e	17.69 ^d
320/0	35.67	43.17	61.67	1.96 ^{bc}	8.11 ^d	17.21 ^{de}
320/40	35.33	41.83	61.33	1.91 ^{cd}	8.96 ^{cd}	19.03 ^c
320/80	35.33	41.83	59.67	1.98 ^{bc}	9.48 ^{abc}	20.68 ^{ab}
320/120	34.67	42.17	59.67	1.98 ^{bc}	10.04 ^{ab}	21.60 ^a
480/0	36	43.83	62.33	1.90 ^{cde}	7.05 ^e	17.09 ^{def}
480/40	35.33	41.83	59.83	2.01 ^b	9.15 ^{bc}	20.29 ^{bc}
480/80	36.33	43	62.33	2.12 ^a	10.33 ^a	21.20 ^{ab}
480/120	35.33	42.83	61.83	2.03 ^b	9.16 ^{bc}	20.45 ^{ab}
LSD _{0.05}	1.47	1.45	1.98	0.07	0.95	1.28
SE	0.15	0.13	0.20	0.01	0.20	0.22
CV (%)	3.63	2.96	2.82	3.33	10.87	6.26

LSD: least significant difference, SE: standard error, and CV: coefficient of variation.

N/P₂O₅, with mean values of 3.85 and 5.01, respectively (Table 3). These findings indicate that the combined application of N and P fertilizers at relatively high rates increased the number of main branches nearly threefold compared with the nil application rate and twofold compared with the application of P and N fertilizers alone.

[Q08] The mean values depicted in Table 3 indicate that the number of clusters per plant increased markedly with increasing fertilization level, peaking at 21.6 clusters, due to the application of 320/120 kg ha⁻¹ N/P₂O₅. This treatment combination increased the number of clusters by 67.2, 49.1, and 33.2% compared with the nil, N alone, and P alone treatments, respectively, at lower rates. The combination of N and P reflected marked variation, which implies a synergetic effect of N and P nutrients on increasing fruit-bearing clusters in tomatoes. However, notably, the benefits of increased fertilizer application tended to plateau beyond the treatment level of 320/120 kg ha⁻¹ N/P₂O₅, and the increasing rate of clusters diminished beyond this level.

INFLUENCES OF N AND P FERTILIZERS ON YIELD AND YIELD COMPONENTS OF TOMATO

The analysis of variance revealed that the main and interaction effects of N and P fertilizers highly significantly influenced ($P < 0.001$) the number of flowers per cluster, the number of fruits per cluster, fruit set percentage, marketable yield, unmarketable yield, and total yield.

The plants growing in the plots fertilized with 320/120 (7.71), 480/80 (7.67), and 320/80 (7.41) kg N/P₂O₅ ha⁻¹ presented the greatest number of flowers per cluster, which were statistically similar to

each other. Plants without fertilizer supplementation and those that received only one type of nutrient (N or P) produced the lowest number of flowers (4.1–5.92). The results indicated a progressive increase in the number of flowers with increasing nutrient levels, implying that the application of optimal N and P promotes floral initiation and development.

The highest fruit number per cluster (6.27) was recorded from the application of 320/120 kg ha⁻¹ N/P₂O₅, which was not significantly different from the fruit number produced with the treatment combinations of 480/80 and 320/80 kg ha⁻¹ N/P₂O₅. The results confirmed a marked increase in fruit number when N and P were applied in combination, each at the optimum level, highlighting the synergetic effects of these nutrients. For example, the fruit number per cluster tripled and doubled compared with the nil and individual applications of N and P at lower rates, respectively. This trend underscores the importance of nutrient availability for fruit set, possibly by facilitating better pollination and fruit retention. However, the responses appeared to plateau beyond the rate of 320/120 kg ha⁻¹ N/P₂O₅, implying a reduction in tomato plant fruiting at excessively high rates of N and P fertilizers.

The fruit set percentage followed a similar trend as the number of fruits per cluster, and it increased substantially with increasing application rates of N/P₂O₅ from 52.06% in the control plot to a maximum of 81.15% in the treatment receiving 320/120 kg ha⁻¹ N/P₂O₅. However, the fruit setting percentage decreased beyond 320/120 kg ha⁻¹ N/P₂O₅, suggesting that overfertilization did not improve fruit setting and could lead to excessive vegetative growth. Furthermore, the treatments with the application of either nutrient presented the lowest fruit setting percentage compared with the combined application. The highest fruit setting percentage at

320/120 kg ha⁻¹ N/P₂O₅ could be attributed mainly to the increased flower number and better resource allocation for increased pollination and fruit setting.

Nitrogen and phosphorous also had a significant influence on the total yield of tomatoes, where 90.7 t ha⁻¹ fruit was recorded from the plot supplied with 320/120 kg ha⁻¹ N/P₂O₅, which was statistically at par with the application of 480/80 kg ha⁻¹ N/P₂O₅ (Table 4). Compared with that of the control and the individual application of nutrients, the total yield clearly increased markedly with increasing fertilizer level. For example, the lowest yields were recorded from plots treated with 0/0, 0/40, and 160/0 kg ha⁻¹ N/P₂O₅, with mean values of 43.34, 51.88, and 59.21 t ha⁻¹, respectively. These findings indicate that, compared with the aforementioned treatments, the application of N/P₂O₅ at 320/120 kg ha⁻¹ increased the total yield by 109.3, 74.8, and 53.2%, respectively.

The marketable fruit yield also followed a similar pattern, and its peak (88.21 t ha⁻¹) was observed in plots fertilized with 320/120 kg ha⁻¹ N/P₂O₅. However, beyond this level, no additional fruit yield was observed (Fig. 3). This revealed a significant increase in marketable yield of 127.8, 86.7, and 60.5% over the yields obtained from 0/0, 0/40, and 160/0 kg ha⁻¹ N/P₂O₅, respectively (Table 4), confirming the substantial impacts of optimal fertilizer combinations on the marketable fruit yield of tomato. Compared with the individual application of 320 N or 120 kg ha⁻¹ P₂O₅, it also increased the marketable yield by 32.1 and 55.4%, respectively. This could be attributed mainly to the synergetic relationship of N and P nutrients, where their combination enhances yield beyond their individual effects.

As depicted in Fig. 4a–c, the regression analysis revealed that the combination of 358/128 kg ha⁻¹ N/P₂O₅ was the optimal combination for the maximum marketable yield of tomato. The

response surface curve (Fig. 3) indicates that the lowest yield (40–50 t/ha) was found with the combination of lower rates, whereas the highest yield (82–86.4 t/ha) was obtained from the combination of N from 350–380 kg ha⁻¹ with P₂O₅ from 125–128 kg ha⁻¹. Moreover, the regression analysis revealed that the marketable yield was highly influenced by the main branch number, flower number, fruit number, fruit setting percentage, average fruit weight, and fruit firmness (Fig. 5a–f).

The data presented in Table 4 clearly revealed that the highest values of unmarketable yields were recorded from the plots without fertilizer application and those with the application of individual N and P nutrients. For instance, unmarketable fruit yields of 4.64, 4.61, 4.51, and 4.26 t ha⁻¹ were obtained from the application of 0/0, 0/40, 0/80, and 160/0 kg ha⁻¹ N/P₂O₅, respectively. Conversely, the lowest unmarketable fruit yield of tomato (2.5 t ha⁻¹) was observed from the plots fertilized with the application of 320/120 kg ha⁻¹ N/P₂O₅, which was statistically equal to the value of 320/80 kg ha⁻¹ N/P₂O₅. The decrease in unmarketable yield with increasing fertilizer levels underscores the importance of balanced nutrition.

EFFECTS OF NP FERTILIZER ON THE PHYSICO-CHEMICAL QUALITY OF TOMATO

The combined ANOVA exhibited that fruit diameter, average fruit weight, fruit firmness, total soluble solids, titratable acidity, and the sugar-to-acidity ratio were significantly influenced ($P < 0.01$) by the main and interaction effects of N and P. However, pericarp thickness and juice pH were not influenced ($P > 0.05$) by the main or interaction effects of N and P fertilizers.

The combined mean value revealed that the greatest fruit diameter (78.34 mm) was recorded from plants supplied with 320/120 fertilizer, whereas the lowest fruit diameter (54.77 mm) was

Table 4. Yield and yield components of tomato as influenced by the interaction of NP fertilizers.

N/P ₂ O ₅ (kg ha ⁻¹)	FIN (Number)	FrN (Number)	FSP (%)	MY (t ha ⁻¹)	UMY (t ha ⁻¹)	TY (t ha ⁻¹)
0/0	4.10 ⁱ	2.12 ^g	52.06 ^j	38.73 ^l	4.64 ^a	43.34 ^l
0/40	4.75 ^h	3.00 ^f	63.17 ^h	47.25 ^k	4.61 ^a	51.88 ^k
0/80	4.97 ^{gh}	3.26 ^{ef}	65.73 ^{gh}	54.32 ^j	4.56 ^{ab}	58.88 ^j
0/120	5.13 ^{gh}	3.45 ^e	67.31 ^{fg}	56.75 ^{ij}	4.17 ^{bcd}	60.92 ^{ij}
160/0	5.28 ^{fg}	3.11 ^{ef}	59.13 ⁱ	54.96 ^j	4.26 ^{abc}	59.21 ^j
160/40	5.93 ^d	4.14 ^{cd}	69.85 ^{ef}	63.24 ^{gh}	4.10 ^{cde}	67.34 ^{gh}
160/80	5.83 ^{de}	4.23 ^{cd}	72.64 ^{bcd}	68.49 ^f	3.81 ^{defgh}	72.30 ^f
160/120	6.12 ^{cd}	4.41 ^{cd}	72.09 ^{cde}	73.93 ^e	3.72 ^{efgh}	77.65 ^e
320/0	5.73 ^{def}	4.06 ^d	70.77 ^{de}	66.78 ^g	3.85 ^{cdefg}	70.63 ^{fg}
320/40	6.17 ^{bcd}	4.55 ^{bc}	73.85 ^{bcd}	75.76 ^{de}	3.66 ^{fgghi}	79.42 ^{de}
320/80	7.41 ^a	5.89 ^a	79.41 ^a	80.88 ^{bc}	2.92 ^k	83.80 ^{bc}
320/120	7.71 ^a	6.27 ^a	81.15 ^a	88.21 ^a	2.50 ^k	90.71 ^a
480/0	5.37 ^{efg}	3.53 ^e	65.80 ^{gh}	60.58 ^{hi}	4.05 ^{cdef}	64.63 ^{hi}
480/40	6.57 ^{bc}	4.95 ^b	75.33 ^b	76.88 ^{cde}	3.54 ^{ghi}	80.42 ^{cde}
480/80	7.67 ^a	6.08 ^a	79.29 ^a	84.4 ^{ab}	3.27 ^{ij}	87.67 ^{ab}
480/120	6.65 ^b	4.96 ^b	74.5 ^{bc}	79.67 ^{cd}	3.43 ^{hi}	83.09 ^{cd}
SE	0.11	0.12	0.81	1.43	0.07	1.37
LSD _{0.05}	0.51	0.42	3.23	4.0	0.41	4.05
CV (%)	7.52	8.66	3.99	6.2	9.51	5.97

FIN: Flower number, FrN: fruit number, FSP: fruit set percentage, MY: marketable yield, UMY: unmarketable yield, TY: total yield, LSD: least significant difference, SE: standard error, and CV: coefficient of variation.

recorded from plants without fertilizer application (Table 5). This finding indicates that the combined application of N and P nutrients at rates of 320/120 kg ha⁻¹ N/P₂O₅ increased the fruit diameter by 43% compared with zero application of nutrients. This could be attributable to the enhanced cell expansion and fruit development due to the synergetic effects of the two nutrients.

As indicated in Table 5, the average fruit weight increased profoundly due to the application of 320/120 kg ha⁻¹ N/P₂O₅ compared with the individual and combined application of nutrients, at both higher and lower rates. The results followed the same pattern as that for fruit diameter, which may be due to the combined effects of balanced nutrients for better nutrient translocation to fruit and fruit growth and development.

The plants supplied with the combination of N/P at the rate of 320/120 kg ha⁻¹ N/P₂O₅ produced fruits with the highest firmness (13.01 N), whereas those without any fertilizer application produced fruits with the lowest (9.6 N) firmness (Table 5). These findings indicate that combined N/P nutrient application at the optimum rate enhances fruit performance and overall quality in addition to increasing fruit yield.

The highest value (4.37 °Brix) of total soluble solid was recorded from the application of 320/120 kg ha⁻¹ N/P₂O₅, which is statistically at par with the application of 480/80, 320/80, 320/40, and 480/40 kg ha⁻¹ N/P₂O₅ (Table 5). On the other hand, the lowest value of total soluble solids was obtained from fruits grown without fertilizer application, and the application of either of the two nutrients occurred at the relatively low rates.

The combined application of 320/40, 320/120, 320/80, and 480/40 kg ha⁻¹ N/P₂O₅ resulted in the highest titratable acidity, with statistically similar values. Titratable acidity decreased beyond the aforementioned levels of N and P nutrients. The lowest titratable acidity was observed in fruits grown with the sole application of N.

These interaction effects suggest that nutrient management can modulate fruit taste attributes. The sugar-to-acidity ratio was also positively influenced by combined N/P fertilization, and the highest

(12.02) and lowest (9.47) values were observed for the 480/80 and 0/0 kg ha⁻¹ N/P₂O₅ combinations, respectively. This highlights that the increased levels of N and P nutrients enhanced the fruit test quality.

ECONOMIC ANALYSIS OF TOMATO YIELD AS INFLUENCED BY N AND P FERTILIZER

The partial budget analysis revealed that the highest net benefit (3,506,745.00 ETB ha⁻¹) was achieved through the application of 320/120 kg ha⁻¹ N/P₂O₅ (Table 2 and Fig. 6). This was followed by the application of 320/80 kg ha⁻¹ N/P₂O₅, which resulted in a net benefit of 3,222,285.00 ETB ha⁻¹. The lowest net benefit (1,568,565.00 ETB ha⁻¹) was recorded from the unfertilized plots.

The highest marginal rate of return (5263.1%) was recorded from the application of 320/40 kg ha⁻¹ N/P₂O₅, indicating that for every ETB, the investment in the application of 320/40 kg ha⁻¹ N/P₂O₅ was approximately 52.63 ETB return. Moreover, all the nondominated treatments exhibited a marginal rate of return exceeding the minimum acceptable threshold of 50–100% for the developing countries, as indicated by CIMMYT (1988). Nonetheless, the treatment comprising 320/120 kg ha⁻¹ N/P₂O₅ had the greatest net benefit, with an acceptable marginal rate of return (2370.50%). This corresponds to a return of 23.75 ETB for every ETB invested, indicating its suitability as the optimal treatment.

Discussion

The results of this study revealed that the fertilization level did not markedly influence the timing of flowering or fruiting initiation in tomatoes, which is in agreement with the findings of other scholars (Kahsay *et al.*, 2016; Mengistu *et al.*, 2017). Studies have also indicated that phenological traits are relatively less sensitive to fertilizer application and are more strongly governed by the genetic makeup of varieties (Kumar *et al.*, 2021; Nishat *et al.*, 2021). This could be attributed to the sensitivity of such traits to environmental factors such as temperature and light rather than nutrient levels.

Fig. 4. Effects of nitrogen and phosphorus rates on marketable yield of tomato; (a) marketable yield response to nitrogen rate; (b) marketable yield response to phosphorus rate, and (c) interaction effects of nitrogen and phosphorus rate on marketable yield.

However, the results of this study negate the findings of Dhiman *et al.* (2018), Parmar *et al.* (2019), and Nishat *et al.* (2021).

[Q14] The relatively high plant height associated with relatively high rates of N/P₂O₅ may be attributable to the fact that N fertilizer promotes the vegetative growth (Hasnain *et al.*, 2020; Hashimi and Habibi, 2021). Compared with the lower rates, variations in plant height and canopy spread have also been reported at moderate-to-high N and P levels (Parmar *et al.*, 2019; Abd-Elsalam *et al.*, 2021; Du *et al.*, 2021), which are in agreement with the findings of this study.

[Q15] Owing to the application of N/P₂O₅ at relatively high rates, the highest main branch may be due to the positive interaction effects of N and P on energy transfer and cellular division, thereby supporting root development and vegetative growth (Abd-Elsalam *et al.*, 2021; Kareem *et al.*, 2021). Our results corroborate the findings of Beyene and Mulu (2019), Rawat *et al.* (2023), and Zhang *et al.* (2024), who demonstrated that the application of optimum rates of N and P significantly increased the branch number and plant architecture.

The benefits of increased fertilizer application tended to plateau beyond the treatment level of 320/120 kg ha⁻¹ N/P₂O₅, and the increasing rate of cluster number diminished beyond this level. A greenhouse trial by Dhiman *et al.* (2018) demonstrated that combined nutrient application at an optimum rate enhances crop performance in tomatoes. Our results also align with the findings of Kumar *et al.* (2017), Beyene and Amare (2019), and Zhang *et al.* (2024), who reported that the optimal availability of N and P nutrients enhances inflorescence development in tomatoes.

The highest fruit setting percentage at 320/120 kg ha⁻¹ N/P₂O₅ could be attributed mainly to the synergetic effect of the two nutrients on the increase in reproductive efficiency, which is likely

driven by increased flower number and better resource allocation for increased pollination and fruit setting. The combined application of N and P fertilizer maximizes floral production due to improved vegetative and hormonal balance (Kumar *et al.*, 2021; Rawat *et al.*, 2023). Similarly, Kareem *et al.* (2020) confirmed the role of N in amino acid and protein synthesis, which is fundamental for flower development, whereas P involvement in energy transfer facilitates cellular proliferation during flowering. In contrast, lower fertilizer applications result in a lower number of flowers (Zhang *et al.*, 2021).

The findings of this study are in line with the results of Bilalis *et al.* (2018), Khan *et al.* (2021), and Saini *et al.* (2023), who reported greater fruit numbers and yields at the optimum supply of N and P nutrients. Other studies have shown a gradual increase in fruit number with increasing N–P levels compared with those without fertilizer and with the application of either nutrient alone (Abu-Alrub *et al.*, 2019; Parmar *et al.*, 2019; Rawat *et al.*, 2023).

The optimum fertilizer application not only promotes flower production but also enhances the transition from flowering to successful fruit setting, possibly by hormonal modulation, including increased cytokinin and auxin levels for better flower induction and fruit retention (Kumar *et al.* (2019). In line with our results, Kareem *et al.* (2020) and Bilalis *et al.* (2018) demonstrated that an adequate supply of N and P nutrients increased carbohydrate synthesis and translocation, providing the energy and substrate necessary for fruit development. Phosphorus availability influences the efficiency of N assimilation, whereas N supply can modulate P uptake and utilization, which promotes optimal growth, flowering, and fruit development (Vance *et al.*, 2003). Moreover, the highest fruit yield observed at this fertilization level can be explained by the increased number of branches, clusters, and flowers and higher

Table 5. Interaction effects of NP fertilizers on the physicochemical quality traits of tomato.

N/P ₂ O ₅ (kg ha ⁻¹)	FD (mm)	AFW (g)	PT (mm)	FF (N)	JpH	TSS (°Brix)	TA	S:A
0/0	54.77 ^j	99.5 ^j	9.01	9.60 ^k	4.39	3.53 ⁱ	0.376 ^{bcd}	9.47 ⁱ
0/40	60.83 ⁱ	115 ⁱ	9.07	10.44 ^j	4.33	3.75 ^h	0.364 ^{fg}	10.30 ^{gh}
0/80	63.16 ^{gh}	122.29 ^{gh}	9.03	10.64 ^{ij}	4.36	3.78 ^{gh}	0.374 ^{cdef}	10.10 ^h
0/120	63.65 ^{gh}	121.56 ^h	9.04	10.83 ^{hi}	4.35	3.92 ^{def}	0.382 ^{abcde}	10.25 ^{gh}
160/0	61.85 ^{hi}	120.44 ^{hi}	9.01	10.49 ^j	4.34	3.83 ^{gh}	0.351 ^g	11.04 ^{cde}
160/40	67.38 ^{ef}	128.61 ^{fg}	9.09	11.14 ^g	4.40	3.97 ^{cd}	0.388 ^{abcd}	10.43 ^{fgh}
160/80	67.53 ^e	132.33 ^{ef}	9.05	12.21 ^f	4.35	4 ^{cd}	0.371 ^{ef}	10.88 ^{cdef}
160/120	72.55 ^{cd}	138.33 ^{de}	9.07	12.33 ^{ef}	4.36	4.03 ^c	0.374 ^{cdef}	10.87 ^{def}
320/0	72.29 ^d	129.56 ^f	9.09	10.88 ^{ghi}	4.37	3.93 ^{de}	0.363 ^{fg}	10.92 ^{cde}
320/40	74.12 ^{bcd}	140.28 ^{cd}	9.09	12.51 ^{cde}	4.38	4.32 ^{ab}	0.391 ^a	11.13 ^{bcd}
320/80	76.31 ^{ab}	149.17 ^{ab}	9.22	12.81 ^{ab}	4.38	4.33 ^a	0.389 ^{abc}	11.33 ^{bcd}
320/120	78.34 ^a	150.67 ^a	9.26	13.01 ^a	4.35	4.37 ^a	0.390 ^{ab}	11.36 ^{bc}
480/0	65.29 ^{fg}	122.55 ^{gh}	9.02	10.10 ^{gh}	4.41	3.85 ^{efg}	0.369 ^{ef}	10.63 ^{efg}
480/40	74.52 ^{bc}	144.28 ^{bcd}	9.17	12.46 ^{def}	4.40	4.32 ^{ab}	0.379 ^{abcde}	11.61 ^{ab}
480/80	76.95 ^a	150.45 ^{ab}	9.24	12.76 ^{abc}	4.36	4.35 ^a	0.374 ^{cdef}	12.02 ^a
480/120	76.13 ^{ab}	145.08 ^{abc}	9.26	12.63 ^{bcd}	4.35	4.23 ^b	0.373 ^{def}	11.55 ^{ab}
SE	0.79	1.55	0.03	0.11	0.01	0.003	0.04	0.17
LSD _{0.05}	2.21	6.36	0.26	0.26	0.07	0.09	0.02	0.48
CV (%)	2.77	4.18	2.49	1.93	1.37	1.87	3.53	3.83

FD: Fruit diameter, AFW: average fruit weight, PT: pericarp thickness, FF: fruit firmness, JpH: juice pH, TA: titratable acidity, TSS: total soluble solid, S: sugar-to-acid ratio, LSD: least significant difference, SE: standard error, and CV: coefficient of variation.

Fig. 6. Second-order polynomial curve fit and regression equation illustrating the effect of nitrogen and phosphorus rates (kg/ha) on net benefit (Birr/ha).

fruit set percentage, average fruit weight, and fruit firmness, as indicated in Fig. 5.

Increasing the fertilization level to 320/120 kg ha⁻¹ N/P₂O₅ greatly increased both the total yield and the marketable yield, whereas further increases did not result in additional yield benefits. This could be due to nutrient saturation, which can lead to nutrient imbalance and osmotic stress (Kumar *et al.*, 2021). Bernados *et al.* (2024) reported that the application of excessive N can lead to lush vegetative growth at the expense of fruiting. The results of this study are consistent with the findings of different scholars, who deduced that optimal N and P fertilization can improve total and marketable yields up to 120 and 135%, respectively (Abu-Alrub *et al.*, 2019; Khan *et al.*, 2021; Yue *et al.*, 2022; Rawat *et al.*, 2023).

These results are supported by those of Tesfay *et al.* (2018), who suggested that an adequate N and P nutrient supply at an optimum combination reduces physiological disorders such as blossom-end rot, cracking, and physiological fruit malformations, which are prevalent under nutrient-deficient conditions. In line with the present results, Sigaye *et al.* (2022) reported that the unmarketable yield increased by 171.8% when tomatoes were grown without fertilizer application compared with the combined application of N and P fertilizers at higher rates. However, these results contradict the findings of Kahsay *et al.* (2016) and Getu *et al.* (2024), who reported a nonsignificant variation with the application of N and P fertilizers.

Research has shown that N influences fruit size by promoting the translocation of nutrients to fruits and that P influences energy transfer and nucleic acid synthesis, which collectively support fruit growth (Kareem *et al.*, 2020; Khan *et al.*, 2021). The present results are supported by the findings of Parmar *et al.* (2019), Gebremedhin *et al.* (2020), and Zhang *et al.* (2024), who noted improved fruit size and weight due to balanced fertilization, highlighting the importance of nutrient management.

The average fruit weight followed the same pattern as that for fruit diameter, which may be due to the combined effects of balanced nutrients for better nutrient translocation to fruit and fruit growth and development, as indicated in Khan *et al.* (2021). Similar to the present findings, Abu-Alrub *et al.* (2019), Kareem *et al.* (2020), Yue *et al.* (2022), and Rawat *et al.* (2023) confirmed that the combined application of N and P nutrients increases fruit weight by 30–60.9% compared with the control and individual applications.

Greater fruit firmness is caused by the combined application of 320/120 kg ha⁻¹ N/P₂O₅ because an adequate supply of N and P nutrients promotes cell wall synthesis and structural integrity (Kaniszewski *et al.*, 2019). The results of this study align with the findings of other scholars who deduced that the application of optimal N and P levels in high-tunnel tomato cultivation facilitates cell wall development and carbohydrate accumulation in fruits, which contributes to increased firmness (Kumar *et al.*, 2019; Zhang *et al.*, 2024).

These findings suggest that the application of optimum fertilizer rates improved carbohydrate accumulation and metabolic activity, which is correlated with increased sweetness and flavor (Mengistu *et al.*, 2017). The present findings are consistent with those of different authors, who reported an increase in total soluble solids of up to 42.3% due to the combined application of N and P nutrients at optimum levels under greenhouse conditions (Khan *et al.*, 2021; Li *et al.*, 2021; Nishat *et al.*, 2021; Singh *et al.*, 2021).

The application of higher N and P resulted in increased juice pH and reduced titratable acidity, leading to a more balanced flavor profile, which is desirable for fresh consumption (Abu-Alrub *et al.*, 2019; Kumar *et al.*, 2019). Moreover, in line with the present results, Kaniszewski *et al.* (2019) and Singh *et al.* (2019) reported a significant variation in titratable acidity in the range of 0.3–0.7. In agreement with the present findings, scholars have reported that balanced N and P fertilizer application elevates the sugar–

acid ratio by increasing carbohydrate accumulation and metabolic activity (Du *et al.*, 2021; Singh *et al.*, 2021).

The nonsignificant response of pericarp thickness and juice pH to the application of N and P fertilizers, both individually and in combination, may be attributed to the fact that such traits are more affected by their genetic makeup and are less responsive to nutrient application. Moreover, these traits may not be affected by this range of nutrient application within the same variety. This finding corroborates other findings that reported a nonsignificant effect on pH due to the combined application of N and P fertilizers (Mengistu *et al.*, 2017).

Conclusion

The results indicated that both the individual and combined applications of N and P fertilizers significantly improved the growth, yield, and quality of tomato, except for the phenological traits, juice pH, and mean pericarp thickness. The combined application of 320/120 kg ha⁻¹ N/P₂O₅ significantly increased the number of clusters per plant, the number of flowers per cluster, number of fruits per cluster, fruit set percentage, marketable yield, total yield, average fruit weight, and total soluble solid parameters of the tomatoes. The combination resulted in the highest marketable yield (88.21 t ha⁻¹) and net benefit (3,506,745.00 ETB ha⁻¹), with an acceptable marginal rate of return (2370.50%). The regression analysis found 358/128 kg ha⁻¹ N/P₂O₅ as the optimum combination for maximum productivity, which is recommended for high-tunnel hybrid tomato production in the Koga Irrigation Scheme of western Amhara, Ethiopia, and areas with similar soil fertility and agroecological conditions. Repeating the study across different locations, including other hybrid tomato varieties, and exploring the effects of additional nutrients on the growth and productivity of tomatoes are also recommended.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

ETHICS STATEMENT

The authors confirm that the research meets any required ethical guidelines, including adherence to the legal requirements of the study country.

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AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

The authors confirm the contributions to the paper as follows: Yekoye Abebeaw, Prof. Melkamu Alemayehu, and Prof. Enyew Adgo contributed to study conception and design; Yekoye Abebeaw contributed to data collection; Yekoye Abebeaw and Dr. Yohannes Fikadu contributed to analysis and interpretation of the results; Yekoye Abebeaw carried out draft manuscript preparation; Prof. Melkamu Alemayehu, Prof. Enyew Adgo, and Dr. Dawit Tsegaye Sissay contributed to writing—review and editing. All the authors reviewed the results and approved the final version of the manuscript.

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DATA AVAILABILITY

The data that support the findings of this study are available upon reasonable request from the corresponding author (Yekoye Abebeaw).

AUTHOR DECLARATION

The author declares that the manuscript has not been submitted to any publisher.

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Author Queries

Chapter No.: 2026-0009

Queries	Details Required	Author's Response
Q01	References "Singh <i>et al.</i> , 2018; Beyene and Amare, 2019" are cited in the text but does not appear in the reference list. Please provide complete reference details for these references in the reference list.	
Q02	Please clarify whether the year for the citation "Kumar <i>et al.</i> , 2021" is "2021a" or "2021b".	
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